

Spectrophotometric Determination of Chromium(VI) Using Gallacetophenone Oxime

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Chromium(VI) reacts with gallacetophenone oxime in acid solution forming a brownish red colour complex. This system obeys Beer's Law in the range 2-16 ppm at 410 nm. The stoichiometry between Cr(VI) and the oxime is established as 1:1. The molar absorptivity and photometric sensitivity are $\epsilon=3.6 \times 10^4$ lit. mole⁻¹cm⁻¹ and 0.015 μ g. cm⁻² respectively. The method is sensitive, simple and rapid,

PHOTOMETRIC determination of microamounts of chromium when present alone or in presence of large amounts of metal ions such as iron and nickel is very important since the metal is present in water as pollutant and a minor constituent in industrial'y important alloys and other complex materials. However, very few rapid colorimetric methods making use of organic reagents are available since chromium in the oxidation state of three is an inert metal ion and in the valency state of six is a powerful oxidant in acid solutions and destroys the organic reagent. Only few colorimetric methods for the determination of Cr(VI) in acid solutions were reported. These include determinations with diphenyl carbazide¹, variamine blue², *o*-dianisidine³, carmoism⁴, starch iodide⁵, resacetophenone oxime⁶ etc.

The present reagent gallacetophenone oxime (2,3,4-trihydroxy acetophenone oxime) was used earlier for the spectrophotometric determination of iron, titanium and uranium⁷ also the gravimetric determination of copper⁸. Further investigations on the analytical applicability of the reagent showed that it forms a brownish red complex with chromium(VI), in fairly acid solutions and common oxidizing agents did not interfere in the colour reaction. Hence, a detailed study of the colour reaction for the possible determination of chromium is carried out and the results are communicated here.

Experimental

Reagents :

Gallacetophenone oxime is prepared following the literature procedure^{9,8} and a 0.1M solution of it is prepared in 50% aqueous ethanol. Chromium(VI) solution (0.1M) is prepared by dissolving the requisite amount of potassium dichromate (AR BDH) in doubly distilled water. All the chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade or equivalent.

Apparatus :

A Beckmann DK-2A UV-visible recording spectrophotometer, an ELICO spectrophotometer Model CI-24 and an ELICO pH meter Model LI-10T for optical and pH measurements respectively.

Results and Discussion

The pH study of the system chromium(VI)-gallacetophenone oxime shows that a brownish red complex is formed within the pH range 1-2 at 410 nm, where chromium(VI) has a little absorbance and the reagent has almost nil absorbance. It is also observed that the colour intensity increased with increase in acidity. Hence the reaction is studied in presence of different acids and the colour intensity in phosphoric acid solution is found to be more compared to other acids and least sensitivity is observed with acetic acid solution. Hence phosphoric acid is chosen as the medium of reaction and maximum absorbance is obtained in the range 0.4M to 0.75M, so all the studies were carried in 0.5M phosphoric acid.

The absorbance of the complex is stable for four hours and for full colour development three fold excess of reagent is necessary and but six fold excess is found suitable for reproducible values. The molar absorptivity of the complex is $\epsilon=3.6 \times 10^4$ lit. mole⁻¹. cm⁻¹.

Procedure :

To various aliquots of the metal ion solution (2-16 ppm) taken in 25 ml measuring flasks, added 6.25 ml of phosphoric acid (2M) and 1 ml of the oxime (0.1M). The contents of the flasks were made upto the mark with doubly distilled water. The absorbance of the resulting solution is measured at 410 nm against the reagent as blank.

Beer's Law range, sensitivity :

A linear plot obtained between absorbance and the amount of chromium(VI) in the range of 2-16 ppm at 410 nm. The photometric sensitivity¹⁰ of the complex is 0.015 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$.

Nature and Stoichiometry of Complex :

Ion exchange studies showed the complex is cationic in nature. Job's continuous variation method, mole ratio method and slope ratio methods showed 1:1 stoichiometry between chromium(VI) and gallacetophenone oxime.

Effect of Foreign ions :

In the determination of 12 ppm of chromium (VI), the effect of diverse ions were studied. Chloride, nitrate, fluoride, borate, tartrate, perchlorate, sulphate, Mn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Fe^{3+} did not interfere even upto 1200 ppm. The tolerance limits of other ions causing an error $\pm 2\%$ are given in parenthesis (in ppm): Cu^{2+} (100); Co^{2+} (200); Cr^{3+} (500); Ni^{2+} (600); Mo^{6+} (70); W^{6+} (40); Ce^{4+} (10); MnO_4^- (220); $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ (160); IO_3^- (250); IO_4^- (90); and however, Ti^{4+} , Zr^{4+} interfere in the colour reaction.

Though the molar absorptivity of diphenyl carbazide ($\epsilon = 4 \times 10^4$) is about eleven times greater than that of the present method ($\epsilon = 3.6 \times 10^3$), the former method suffers from the very disadvantage that the reagent is unstable and divergent opinions are available on the stability of diphenyl carbazide reagent. Urone¹¹ stated that its stability depends greatly on the type and purity of the solvent used and the aqueous solutions were described to be the least stable. According to Allen¹² the quality of the solid diphenyl carbazide varies with the supplier and depends upon the procedure, symmetrical and unsymmetrical diphenyl carbazides¹³ are formed. On the other hand, the present reagent gallacetophenone oxime is very stable over a long period both in solid state and in solution. Further, the complex formation is instantaneous, and sufficiently stable. Unlike diphenyl carbazide method, the excess oxidants do not interfere to a sufficient amount in this method. And large amounts of

permanganate were tolerated in presence of excess reagent. Since sulphate ion did not interfere when present in large amounts, this method is great advantage in the analysis of chrome ores and chromium alloys and steels since they are usually dissolved in $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 - \text{H}_3\text{PO}_4$ acids mixture¹⁴. And also the present method is more sensitive than resacetophenone oxime⁶.

However, vanadium(V) interferes when the amount exceeds the amount of Cr(VI). But this interference is minimised by extraction with 8-hydroxy quinoline into chloroform at pH⁴.

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